

**METHODS OF DEVELOPING TASKS WORKING SKILLS IN FUTURE UZBEK
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Annotation. The article describes the reasons, necessity, goals and tasks of developing a methodology for creating educational tasks and using them effectively for future native language and literature teachers. Also, the distinction of educational tasks in terms of tasks, the reaction to the scientific researches carried out on them until now, the conclusions and proposals for the solution of the problem were presented.

Key words: future specialists, Uzbek language, literature, educational tasks, questions, exercises and assignments, knowledge, skills, competence.

Introduction

In the training of future native language and literature teachers, it is necessary to first of all inform them about the content and types of educational tasks. First, future professionals should understand the role of questions, exercises and tasks in language education. In this case, educational tasks are an important factor that creates the content of education.

In this regard, it should be noted that a number of scientists in pedagogy have carried out important scientific research, in particular, the issue of determining the types and tasks of educational tasks in language education has been discussed by I.A.Allayorov, O.R.Rozikov, R.Ibragimov, B.R.Adizov, M.H.Mahmudov¹ problems of increasing student activity through assignments were also studied. Russian pedagogues A.N.Leontev, J.A.Ponomarev, S.L.Rubenstein, Australian scientist Jacques Richards² researched educational tasks in the teaching of English as a mother tongue and as a second language. His approaches to the description and classification of educational tasks are used worldwide.

¹ Маҳмудов М.Ҳ. Таълимни дидактик лойиҳалашнинг назарий асослари. Пед. фанл. докт. илм. дараж. олиш учун ёзилган дисс. автореферати. –Т.: 2004. -42 б. Рубинштейн С. Л. проблемы общей психологии. - Москва: Педагогика, 1976. -416 С. Леонтьев А. Н. проблемы развития психики. - Москва: Педагогика, 1972. -576 С.

It is known that in language textbooks, the terms “exercise”, “question” and “assignment” are mainly used in the natural and concrete sciences. All of them are a type of work included in educational tasks, and this term is also interpreted as educational tasks in some studies.

As we mentioned above, the main goal of language education is the differentiation of the content and tasks of educational tasks. For this reason, we thought it would be good to discuss the terms “exercise”, “question”, “assignment” separately in terms of content and application. In our opinion, this is the most comprehensive “assignment”, and in textbooks and manuals it includes a question and an exercise.

Success cannot be achieved without national values, including perfect knowledge of the mother tongue. That is why the question of what and how to teach in the methodology of teaching the mother tongue has been a problem from ancient times to the present day. This is a natural situation, since development depends on methodology, time makes its demands, and methodology fulfills this order. That is why the question of what and how to teach is of constant relevance³. In this regard, it is appropriate to present the issue of educational tasks in the context of “Mother Tongue” textbooks, to differentiate educational tasks in terms of tasks, and to analyze the attitude to educational tasks.

It can be noted that Q.Husanboeva’s views on including the teacher in the educational content are the right approach. In fact, it is important for the teacher to set an example directly in the development of students’ literary pronunciation skills in the necessary places in mother tongue education, especially in controlling the exercises performed in the classroom. In T.Ziyadova’s research on the formation of text creation competencies in students, the main component of text creation technology was also considered to be educational tasks, but in this study, exercises and tasks were not seriously differentiated⁴.

G.Hamroyev put forward the issue of differentiating educational tasks according to the task they perform. In our opinion, the assignment includes an exercise and a question, guides the student to acquire knowledge, participates in evaluation; is the main educational task that organizes the formation of skills through repetition-based exercises. Based on long-term observations and analysis, it can be concluded that the educational tasks called exercises in the “Mother language” textbooks are not exercises, that is, they do not meet the requirements of the exercise. In fact, exercise is not a means of imparting knowledge; it should be used to develop skills and competences.

³ Ҳамроев Ғ. Она тили ўқитишнинг самарали усуллари. Ўқитувчилар учун методик қўлланма. –Т.: Баёз. 2018. 18-б.

⁴ Зиёдова Т.У. Матн яратиш технологияси. – Т.: Фан, 2007. 23-б.

And the task should be used to acquire knowledge, organize training and evaluate the acquired knowledge and skills, and the question should encourage the student to think and try. In practice, they are used in a mixed manner. For this reason, even if the methods and content of textbooks are updated, the efficiency of the lesson does not increase significantly, and speech skills are not fully developed⁵. In this sense, future native language and literature teachers should effectively use educational tasks to reveal the content of native language education and develop speaking skills, special attention should be paid to the creation of educational tasks and their use in the educational process.

Teachers should know how to create pragmatic learning tasks that connect students with real life in mother tongue and literature classes and use them effectively in classes.

Future teachers must have the skills and qualifications to create and evaluate high-quality educational assignments. Most of the teachers cannot create educational tasks that objectively evaluate the knowledge and skills of the students. As a result, the student's speech competence does not develop.

In order to check the student's knowledge and acquired skills in the native language and literature classes, the teacher should develop a system of well-thought-out tasks. One of the factors that have a negative impact on the student's attitude to the lesson, which is encountered in practice, is giving everyone a task of the same level and content. In this regard, it is necessary to apply a new approach. That is, giving the group of students at least three different tasks of different levels, instead of one task as before, can give a positive result.

In this regard, G.Hamroyev⁶ also makes special mention of it in his research. Professor Jacques Richards, a pedagogue and art historian who conducts extensive research on English language teaching methods, says that "exercises are coherent, comprehensive, and include reading comprehension and writing skills. Tasks include any type of activity that results not only in learning the language, but also in doing something with the language.

As you can see, each term has its own meaning. In other words, If an exercise means acquiring the skills and competences expected from this exercise by repeating a specific action several times, then an assignment means a task that is given to a person, including a student, to perform once in order to strengthen a topic⁷.

Tasks used in mother tongue education are initially divided into two types:

⁵ Hamroyev G'. Ona tilidan o'quv topshiriqlari tuzish metodikasi. –Toshkent. Donishmand ziyosi. 2021. 154 b.

⁶ <https://www.professorjackrichards.com/category/news/>

⁷ Хамроев Ф. Умумий ўрта таълим тизимида фонетикага доир ўқув материалларнинг методик таъминотини такомиллаштириш. Пед. фан. фал.док.дисс. – Самарқанд, 2019. – 144 б.

1. Traditional tasks.
2. Modern tasks.

Traditional tasks are also used in the educational process. The importance of this task can be seen from the fact that it has been implemented so far. Traditional assignments are still used in mother tongue and Uzbek language classes. “Find words belonging to the noun group from the given sentences”, “Find and describe vowels from the given text” among several tasks that do not serve the formation of speaking skills, such as “Identify misspelled words from the given text”, “Determine which of the following sentences use punctuation marks inappropriately” although traditional, you can find tasks that serve to develop speaking skills. But there are not many such educational assignments; moreover, they are not given systematically based on certain criteria.

What is the need for modern tasks? Today, the task of educating independent, critical, new-thinking people is an important task for mother tongue education. At the same time as teaching the Uzbek language, it is necessary to develop the skills of reflection, observation and critical attitude in the student.

An example of the use of educational tasks is developed below, and task types of tasks are presented by working on the selected text. Tasks, as mentioned, are first used in the formation of knowledge, skills and abilities, and then as a means of testing acquired knowledge and acquired skills and abilities.

Future native language and literature teachers should thoroughly master the methodology of creating educational tasks and using them correctly before attending classes. Otherwise, the effectiveness of the lesson will not increase. The student's linguistic and speech competences do not develop as expected. Future teachers of Uzbek language and literature of higher educational institutions should be given theoretical knowledge and practical skills in creating and using educational assignments.

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